

Sensitivity of CT dimensional measurements to rotation stage errors

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Abstract

Error motions of the rotation stage in X-ray computed tomography instruments can affect the quality of measurements performed on the acquired data. The effects of rotation stage errors are evaluated for simulated CT measurements of a simple test object at various magnification positions. The magnitude and functional behavior of simulated stage errors correspond to the acceptance limits in the specifications of the Newport RVS80CC rotation stage employed by a Nikon 225kV CT system. Dimensional errors in the simulated CT measurements in the presence of rotation stage errors are compared to the same measurements simulated in the absence thereof. A discussion on the sensitivity of CT measurements to rotation stage errors is given.

Keywords: dimensional measurements, rotation stage errors, cone-beam computed tomography

1 Introduction

The cone-beam tomographic reconstruction step converts the set of acquired two-dimensional radiographic images to a three-dimensional X-ray attenuation map of the measurement volume. One of the more common tomographic reconstruction algorithms for cone-beam systems with two-dimensional flat panel detectors is the filtered backprojection algorithm [1], also known as Feldkamp-Davis-Kress (FDK) after the three researchers at the Ford Motor Company who in 1984 originally proposed the reconstruction technique. The practical implementation of the FDK algorithm has evolved with new knowledge and hardware, both for radiographic acquisition, filtering methods, and capacity of reconstruction computers. However, the geometrical concept of the backprojection step has remained largely unchanged. For each angular position of the sample rotation stage, the measured X-ray intensity at each pixel in the radiographic image is back projected as a linear trajectory from the corresponding pixel position to the X-ray focal spot (Figure 1). Each trajectory traces a path through the measurement volume, which is defined as a three-dimensional array of voxels, thereby intersecting a series of voxels along that path. Attenuation values for each voxel are calculated from the collection of radiographic intensities, the back projected trajectories of which intersect that voxel.

Figure 1: Backprojection of radiographic pixels through the voxel space.

The stage with which the measured sample is rotated can have indexing errors and rotational error motions [2]. Discrepancies between the actual position and orientation of the measured sample and the position and orientation of the voxel space assumed in the backprojection step can result in dimensional errors of the reconstructed volumetric data. The sensitivity of dimensional measurements to rotation stage indexing errors and error motions is studied here for simulated CT data of a test object. Acquisitions are repeated for several magnification positions and the test object is appropriately scaled to preserve the test object-to-voxel size ratio between scans. This scaling of the test object allows us to scale the dimensional measurements to approximate the size of typical test objects imaged at the given magnification position; magnitude of rotation stage errors do not change with magnification position.

The test object consists of 27 spheres arranged in a helical trajectory of two helical turns at a fixed radius from a common cylindrical axis (Figure 2). Such an object can be manufactured, for example, by attaching highly X-ray absorptive spheres (e.g. steel or zirconia) to a cylindrical support with significantly lower X-ray absorption (e.g. a carbon fiber tube), as shown in [3]. In this simulation study, the test object is modelled as a set of spheres ‘floating’ in space to remove the effects that absorption and scatter from other objects would contribute to dimensional measurements on the reconstructed spheres. Spheres are numbered sequentially from the top of the helix to the bottom. The positions of the spheres are defined in cylindrical coordinates: radius r , angular position β about the cylindrical axis, and height h along cylindrical axis.

The following dimensions are specified for the sphere positions and diameter are defined for a magnification of 1 in the simulated CT instrument (see Table 5 for the relevant geometrical parameters). The test object dimensions for each simulated magnification position (see Table 4) are given by the following values divided by the respective magnification factor. The diameter of the spheres is 9.416 mm. All spheres are located at a fixed radius $r = R$ from the cylindrical axis, where $R = 105.304$ mm. The angular spacing between adjacent spheres $\Delta\beta$ is constant, where $\Delta\beta = (720/26)^\circ$. Spheres 1, 14, and 27 are located at angular positions $\beta_1 = 0^\circ$, $\beta_{14} = 360^\circ$, and $\beta_{27} = 720^\circ$, respectively. Angular spacing does not change with magnification. The height h of each sphere is defined with respect to sphere 1; these values are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2: The test object and geometrical parameterization.

Sphere	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Height /mm	0.00	15.54	30.60	45.20	59.32	73.44	85.21	95.10	104.99
Sphere	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Height /mm	114.88	124.29	133.71	143.12	152.54	161.96	171.37	180.79	190.20
Sphere	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
Height /mm	200.09	209.98	219.86	231.63	245.76	259.88	274.48	289.54	305.08

Table 1. Height along cylindrical axis from sphere 1 of each sphere in the test object at a magnification of 1 for the CT instrument simulated in this study. The scaled heights for simulated magnification positions are given by the values in this table divided by the respective magnification factor.

2 Parameterization of rotation stage errors

A right-handed global coordinate system for typical cone-beam computed tomography instruments is defined. The X-ray source focal spot is the origin of the global coordinate frame. The Z axis is coincident with the magnification axis, which is defined as the line from the source focal spot that intersects the detector perpendicularly to its plane. The Y axis is parallel to the sample stage axis of rotation and the X axis follows the right-handed screw rule, i.e. $(X \times Y) = Z$. The origin of a local detector coordinate frame is located at the top left corner of the active detector area. In an aligned system, the detector horizontal axis U is parallel to the X axis, while the detector vertical axis is anti-parallel to the Y axis. The orthogonal translations of the sample stage manipulator are parallel to the X, Y, and Z axes of the global coordinate frame. Rotation stage errors in CT are unintended changes in position and orientation of the sample stage as a function of rotation position n . It should be noted that zero-order rotation stage errors, i.e. errors that are constant as a function of rotation position n , do not affect CT measurements; therefore, only higher order rotation stage errors are modelled. The following parameterization of rotation stage errors is accompanied by the diagrams in Figure 3. The functions and magnitudes of the modelled rotation stage errors are shown in Table 2 and correspond to the observed behaviors and acceptance limits, respectively, in the technical specification of a Newport RVS80CC employed in a Nikon 225kV CT system.

Indexing error δ is the error between the assumed rotation angle α_{index} and actual rotation angle α_{actual} about the sample stage axis of rotation. In this study, indexing error is modelled as a first order harmonic component and a smaller, superimposed random component. Axial error motion τ_Y is a translation of the sample stage along its axis of rotation. Radial error motion is a translation of the sample stage along a plane orthogonal to the sample stage axis of rotation. Two parameters, τ_X along the global X axis and τ_Z along the global Z axis, are used to parameterize radial error motion. Axial and radial error motions are randomly sampled from uniform distributions. Tilt error is a tilt of the sample stage surface normal with respect to the sample stage axis of rotation. This error motion is parameterized by two angles: ξ denotes the direction of the unit vector along the XZ plane about which the tilt error motion occurs and γ denotes the magnitude of the tilt. Tilt error is intrinsic to the rotating frame of the sample stage; therefore, ξ rotates with the axis of rotation from an initial position ξ_0 . Modelling of tilt magnitude γ consists of two systematic components: a half order harmonic tilt (repeats once every 720° of stage rotation) and a thirteenth order harmonic tilt due to e.g. imperfect ball bearings between stage stator and rotor. The modelled center of rotation for tilt error motion is located at the center of the rotation stage stator assembly.

Figure 3: Rotation stage errors are unintended shifts and tilts of the sample rotation stage that vary with rotation position n . In this simulation study, the following rotation stage errors are modelled: angular indexing error, axial and radial error motions, and tilt error.

Rotation stage error	Parameter	Function	Magnitude
Indexing error	$\delta_1(n)$	First order harmonic	± 0.0027 degrees
	$\delta_R(n)$	Random	± 0.0003 degrees
Tilt error motion	$\gamma_{1/2}(n)$	Half-order harmonic	± 18 μ radians
	$\gamma_{13}(n)$	Thirteenth-order harmonic	± 2 μ radians
	$\xi(n)$	Linear	$\xi(n) = \xi_0 + \alpha(n)$
Radial error motion (X)	$\tau_X(n)$	Random	± 2 μ m
Radial error motion (Z)	$\tau_Z(n)$	Random	± 2 μ m
Axial error motion	$\tau_Y(n)$	Random	± 2 μ m

Table 2. Functions and magnitudes for the modelled rotation stage errors. ‘Random’ denotes random sampling from a uniform distribution, the interval $[-a,+a]$ of which is given by the values in the corresponding magnitude column. The magnitude for harmonic error components corresponds to the maximum and minimum intensity of the corresponding waveform.

3 Simulation and data analysis

Analytical (ray-tracing) software Scorpius XLab[®] [4] is used to simulate the radiographic acquisition and tomographic reconstruction of the test object. The constant geometrical parameters of the simulated CT system are shown in Table 3, where SDD is the source-to-detector distance. Five CT acquisitions are simulated, each at a different position of the sample stage along the magnification axis. The source-to-rotation axis distance (SRD) and corresponding magnification for each simulated acquisition are shown in Table 4. Filament current and X-ray tube acceleration voltage were chosen for each acquisition to provide similar contrast and brightness in the simulated radiographs among all acquisitions.

Parameter	Value
Detector size	400 mm \times 400 mm
Number of pixels	2000 \times 2000
Pixel size	0.2 mm \times 0.2 mm
SDD	1177 mm
Projections	720

Table 3: Constant parameters of the simulated CT system.

Acquisition	1	2	3	4	5	6
SRD	250 mm	25 mm	12.5 mm	6 mm	4.5 mm	3 mm
Magnification	4.71	47.08	94.16	196.17	261.56	392.33

Table 4: Source-to-rotation axis distance and magnification for five simulated acquisitions.

For each acquisition, the test object is scaled such that the ratio of test object (sphere size and sphere positions) to voxel size is constant among all acquisitions. Each acquisition is simulated once under ideal rotation of the sample stage and once in the presence of rotation stage errors. Each simulated dataset is then tomographically reconstructed by a filtered backprojection (Feldkamp type) algorithm [1] in Scorpius XLab[®]. The built-in reconstruction applies a Shepp-Logan filter [5] to the radiographic images prior to backprojection into the volume, in which bilinear interpolation [6] is used. Reconstructed volumes consist of 1999 (X) \times 2000 (Y) \times 1999 (Z) voxels. Voxel sizes and the size of measurement volumes are shown for each acquisition in Table 5. Processing of the volumetric datasets is performed in VGStudio MAX 3.0 (Volume Graphics GmbH, Germany). Surfaces are generated from the volumetric models by applying advanced (local) surface determination to automatically-determined isosurface grey values. The local deviation search distance in the advanced surface determination is set to the default 4 voxels. The surface model is converted to three-dimensional point coordinates by applying surface sampling at 1 voxel intervals along each coordinate direction. Point coordinates corresponding to each sphere in the test object are isolated and a sphere is least-squares fit. The parameters of the fit spheres; namely sphere center, radius, and residuals; are analyzed in the following section.

Acquisition		1	2	3	4	5	6
Voxel size / μm	X	41.90	4.19	2.10	1.01	0.75	0.50
	Y	35.36	3.54	1.77	0.85	0.64	0.42
	Z	41.90	4.19	2.10	1.01	0.75	0.50
Measurement volume /mm	X	83.76	8.38	4.20	2.02	1.50	1.00
	Y	70.72	7.08	3.54	1.70	1.28	0.84
	Z	83.76	8.38	4.20	2.02	1.50	1.00
Local surface determination search distance		4 voxels					
Surface sampling interval (X \times Y \times Z)		1 \times 1 \times 1 voxels					

Table 5: Parameters of the reconstructed volumes, surface determination search distance, and surface sampling interval for all acquisitions.

4 Results

Measured results from the acquisition with rotation stage errors are compared to the same results from acquisition with ideal rotation. Since the size of the measured features vary among acquisitions, errors (differences) between the datasets are presented as percent of the features measured under ideal rotation. The following results indicate that, as can be expected, the sensitivity of dimensional measurements given constant rotation stage errors increases with magnification. The scope of this study is to investigate the relationship between the modelled rotation stage errors and measurements made at the upper magnification limits of the simulated instrument. A typical measurand in objects consisting of multiple spheres is the error in sphere center-to-center distances from a chosen reference sphere to all other spheres. However, error in the position of the chosen reference sphere will be present in all center-to-center distance errors, thereby shedding doubt on the exemplariness of the measurand to describe general length errors in the measurement volume. An alternative is to calculate distances to sphere centers from a new reference point, defined by the mean coordinates over all spheres in a given dataset. These distances are hereby referred to as mean-to-sphere center distances (M2C). Errors in M2C as a result of rotation errors are shown as percent of the measured length from ideal rotation in Figure 4. M2C errors do not exceed one tenth of a percent with respect to the measured distances under ideal rotation. M2C errors indicate sensitivity to rotation stage errors starting at acquisition 2, corresponding to a voxel size of approximately 4 μm . The maximum observed error in acquisition 2 is one fortieth of a percent, which corresponds to a maximum expected length measurement error (from one end of the volume to the opposite) of approximately 4 μm . Maximum expected length measurement errors over the reconstructed volumes for acquisitions 3, 4, 5, and 6 are approximately 3 μm , 2 μm , 3 μm , and 1.8 μm , respectively. Errors in sphere fit radii due to rotation errors are presented in Figure 5 as percent of the radii measured with ideal rotation. Noticeable effects appear by acquisition 4, corresponding to a voxel size of approximately 1 μm . These effects increase with magnification to approximately 1.5 % error at acquisition 6. Sphere fit radius errors are similar for all spheres within a given acquisition. Maximum observed radius errors for acquisitions 4, 5, and 6 are 0.084 μm on 24 μm radii, 0.09 μm on 18 μm radii, and 0.18 μm on 12 μm radii, respectively.

Figure 4: Error due to rotation error motions in mean-to-sphere center distances (M2C) as percent of measured M2C under ideal rotation for acquisitions 1 to 6.

Figure 5: Radius errors due to rotation error motions as percent of measured radii under ideal rotations for acquisitions 1 to 6.

Form errors in the reconstructed spheres can be discerned by observing the residuals between surface points and the corresponding fit sphere. These residuals are shown as percent of sphere radii measured with ideal rotation in histogram form in Figure 6. Results are shown separately for acquisitions with ideal rotation and acquisitions with rotation errors, albeit side by side for comparison. The Y axis in the histograms corresponds to relative frequency; therefore, no units are shown. The 2.5 % and 97.5 % quantiles are shown in Table 6, corresponding to the lower and upper limits, respectively, for the central 95 % of all residual values in a given dataset. The results indicate that noticeable differences in sphere form due to rotation errors appear from acquisition 3, corresponding to a voxel size of approximately 2 μm .

Figure 6: Histograms for residuals between reconstructed sphere surface points and sphere fit as percent of measured radii under ideal rotation for acquisitions 1 to 6.

Sphere fit residuals / %		Acquisition					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Ideal rotation	2.5 %	-0.30	-0.27	-0.27	-0.26	-0.26	-0.27
	97.5 %	0.27	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.23	0.22
With rotation errors	2.5 %	-0.30	-0.27	-0.38	-0.75	-1.11	-2.52
	97.5 %	0.27	0.24	0.36	0.86	1.36	2.59

Table 6: Distribution of sphere fit residuals as percent of measured radii under ideal rotation. The distribution is indicated by the 2.5 % and 97.5 % quantiles, corresponding to the lower and upper limits, respectively, for 95 % of observed residuals.

5 Discussion

The results in this study indicate that the error behaviors as indicated by the specifications of the rotation stage employed in a Nikon 225kV CT system introduce noticeable effects on CT measurements for magnifications above 50, corresponding to voxel sizes below 4 μm . For the CT system in this study, these magnifications correspond to measurement volumes below 8 mm \times 8 mm \times 8 mm, where maximum expected measurement errors were approximately equivalent to the length of one voxel. Sphere radius and form errors were noticeable below magnifications of approximately 100 and 200, respectively. In this measurement domain, effects due to the finite size of the focal spot are overwhelmingly larger than the observed effects due to rotation stage errors. Understanding the sensitivity of measurements to certain error sources can help users prioritize error mapping of their measuring instrument. In this simulation study, it is shown that the effects of rotation stage errors are relatively small for measurements made on “macro” CT instruments, such as the one modelled here. A similar study should be extended to rotation stage errors in micro- and nano-CT systems.

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